

THE ENTOMOFAUNA OF THE LOW HILLS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14863365>

Abstract: This article focuses on the preservation of landscapes and biodiversity in the low hills of Karakalpakstan, the optimization of nature management, and the inventory of certain insect groups, especially in desert regions with strong anthropogenic influences. The current status of the insect species composition in the region was analyzed, and for the first time, 137 species belonging to 19 orders, 63 families, and 112 genera were identified. Additionally, based on the abundance and density of insects in the region, it was determined that 67 species are permanent or freely living, 29 species are widespread, 4 species are in a state of decline, 23 species are rare, 12 species are very rare, and 2 species are included in the Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Entomofauna, class, order, taxonomic structure, transformed, anthropogenic impact.

Introduction: In recent years, the sharp changes in climate conditions occurring globally have naturally impacted the regional entomofauna. Particularly, the process of desertification and increased anthropogenic pressure have led to the extinction of unique and endemic species, while also contributing to the introduction of invasive species. The taxonomic structure of insect species allows the identification of similarities and differences through the use of mathematical methods to classify all the taxa within the class and order.

Modern systematists divide insects (Insecta) into 46 orders based on morphological and some bioecological characteristics (Zhang, 2013). The data presented below provides a brief overview of the results of studies conducted on various distributions and the biology of species, including descriptions of general and high-level taxa, as well as their diversity in the research field. Research conducted from 2020 to 2024 shows that in the natural and anthropogenic areas of the low hills of Karakalpakstan (Qaratov, Sulton Vays, Qo'shqanataw'), 137 species, 19 orders, 63 families, and 112 genera of insects were identified. The large number of species and the biological diversity of insects play an important role in nature and human life (Table 1).

Table 1
Taxonomic Structure of the Entomofauna of the Low Hills of Karakalpakstan

№	Family	Number of Genera	%	Number of Species	%
1.	Zygentoma				
	Lepismatidae	1		1	0.72
2.	Ephemeroptera				
	Baetidae	1		4	2.9
	Heptageniidae	1		1	0.72
	Caenidae	1		2	1.45
	Ephemerellidae	1		1	0.72
3.	Trichoptera				
	Leptoceridae	1		1	0.72
4.	Odonato				
	Aeshnidae	1		2	1.45
	Gomphidae	2		2	1.45
	Libellulidae	2		2	1.45
5.	Blattoptera				
	Polyphagidae	1		1	0.72
	Hodotermitidae	1	1.3		0.72
6	Mantoptera				
	Mantidae	3	2.6	3	1.6
7.	Dermoptera				
	Embiidae	1		1	0.72
8.	Phasmoptera				
	Bacillidae	1		1	0.72
9.	Orthoptera				
	Tettigoniidae	1		1	0.72
	Gryllidae	3		3	1.3
	Gryllotalpidae	1		1	0.72
	Pyrgomorphidae	1		1	0.72
	Pamphagidae	1		1	0.72
	Dericorythidae	1		2	1.45
	Acrididae	11		14	10.3
10.	Phthiraptera				
	Trichodectidae	1		1	0.72
11.	Homoptera				
	Cixiidae	1		1	0.72
	Tettigometridae	1		1	0.72

Aphididae	2		2	1.45
12.	Thysanoptera			
Phlaeothripidae	1		1	0.72
13.	Heteroptera			
Nabidae	1		2	1.45
Anthocoridae	1		1	0.72
Miridae	2		2	1.45
Reduviidae	1		2	1.45
Lygaeidae	1		1	0.72
Saldidae	1		1	0.72
Rhopalidae	1		1	0.72
Pentatomidae	1		1	0.72
Veliidae	1		1	0.72
14.	Neuroptera			
Myrmeleontidae	1		1	0.72
15.	Coleoptera			
Carabidae	9		13	9.48
Buprestidae	2		2	1.45
Tenebrionidae	8		10	7.29
Scarabaeidae	5		9	6.56
Meloidae	1		2	1.45
Chrysomelidae	4		4	2.9
Curculionidae	5		5	3.64
16.	Lepidoptera			
Cossidae	3		3	2.18
Erebidae	1		3	2.18
Noctuidae	1		1	0.72
Cupridinidae	1		1	0.72
Nymphalidae	1		1	0.72
17.	Hymenoptera			
Vespidae	2		3	2.18
Sphecidae	2		2	1.45
Formicidae	3		5	3.64
18.	Siphonaptera			
Pulicidae	1		1	0.72
19.	Diptera			
Asilidae	1		1	0.72
Syrpidae	1		1	0.72
Chironomidae	1		1	0.72
Hippoboscidae	1		1	0.72
Ceratopogonidae	1		1	0.72
Mysidae	1		1	0.72

Total	63	117	100	137	100
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In the low hills of Karakalpakstan, a total of 137 species and subspecies of insects have been identified. The results of the taxonomic structure study of the identified species' fauna indicate that the insect fauna of this region belongs to 18 orders and 63 families, as recorded in the research findings. The number of families and percentage indicators are presented in Figure 1.

From the provided data, it is clear that mayflies (Ephemeroptera) include four families, four genera, and nine species, dragonflies (Odonato) consist of three families, five genera, and six species, and grasshoppers (Orthoptera) include seven families, 19 genera, and 23 species. The number of genera and percentage indicators are shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 1. The number of families and percentage indicators

Figure 2. The number of genera and percentage indicators

Homoptera includes 3 families, 4 subfamilies, and 4 species. **Heteroptera (True Bugs)** consists of 9 families, 10 subfamilies, and 45 species. The largest group is **Coleoptera (Beetles)**, which comprises 7 families, 29 subfamilies, and 55 species. **Lepidoptera (Moths and Butterflies)** includes 5 families, 7 subfamilies, and 9 species. **Hymenoptera (Bees, Wasps, and Ants)** consists of 3 families, 7 subfamilies, and 10 species. **Diptera (Flies)** contains 6 families, 6 subfamilies, and 6 species. The **Mantoptera** (Mantis-like insects) includes 1 family, 1 subfamily, and 3 species, while the least abundant group, **Zygentoma (Silverfish)**, has 1 family, 1 subfamily, and 1 species. The total number of species and their percentage distribution are shown in Figure 3.

Additionally, the presence of **Blattoptera (Cockroaches)**, **Isoptera (Termites)**, **Dermoptera (Earwigs)**, **Phasmoptera (Walking Sticks)**, **Phthiraptera (Lice)**, **Thysanoptera (Thrips)**, **Trichoptera (Caddisflies)**, **Neuroptera (Alderflies)**, and **Siphonaptera (Fleas)** has been confirmed in the studied area.

Figure 3. The number of species and percentage

In conclusion, it can be stated that the current state of the insect species composition in the low hills of Karakalpakstan has been analyzed, and for the first time, it has been determined that there are 137 species belonging to 19 orders, 63 families, and 112 genera. To preserve the landscape and biological diversity of the region, optimize nature management, and especially in areas with strong anthropogenic transformation in desert conditions, the inventory of certain insect groups has been carried out. According to the findings, in the southern Aral Sea region, based on the number and density of winged insects, 67 species are considered permanent or free-living, 29 species are widespread, 4 species are in a state of decline, 23 species are rare, 12 species are very rare, and 2 species are included in the Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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